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BYPASSING ETHICS VIA DESIGN

ETHICAL DISCOURSES IN THE ROAD DESIGN PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

In September 1996 two people were killed shortly after the Bedford Southern Bypass in the UK was first opened to traffic. The deaths sparked discussion about the design of the bypass and this paper draws together the different discourses involving ethics and the process of design. The paper begins by noting theoretical similarities between the areas of design and ethics, it goes on to discuss the concept of 'moral imagination'. Two discourses are then presented, the first describing the reaction to the deaths, the second looking at original documentation from the bypass design process. The paper concludes that designers, through exercising their imagination in designing, are able to resolve ethical problems without relying on the ethical discourses prevalent in both philosophy on the one hand, and the media on the other, which tend to rely on individual accounts of imagination and explicit ethical awareness. The discourse of the design process suggests a more social idea of imagination (past and present) and design judgment that, although having a strong aesthetic component to it, is able to address ethical issues.

Keywords: Design Processes, Design Ethics, Design Case Studies, Design Thinking

INTRODUCTION

The beginning of Douglas Adam's novel *The Hitchhiker's Guide to the Galaxy* describes the demolition of planet Earth to make way for a new 'hyperspace express route'. The Vogon captain of the spaceship, charged with the demolition, announces that, as no objections to the bypass had been received, and since the plans for the bypass had been posted at the local planning office on Alpha Centauri for '50 Earth years', the Earth will be demolished, which it promptly is. The example may

be extreme, but it reveals the often tacit link between design and ethics. The process of making things better through design - in this case creating a new hyperspace express route - often, and arguably always, comes with an ethical cost.

The subject areas of design theory and ethical theory display close structural similarities. Both areas are concerned with what people *should* do, by developing normative (prescriptive) theories and models for behaviour and organisation. They are also concerned with what people *actually* do, by describing various practices and procedures. In both fields there is also a meta-level discussion about the concepts used in prescription and description. In design theory this might be a discussion about the concept of a 'function', for example, while in the ethical area this might be a debate about how 'rights' are conceptualised. Crucially, the practical outcome of both these theoretical areas is to help make life better through considered action.

Design is being used here in a wide sense, encompassing many sub-areas - architectural design, engineering design, product design, for example. However, if one accepts that both ethics and design can both be conceived as subjects sharing an ethical purpose, then the overarching question is how design activity - which is rarely explicit about the type of ethical things it deals with - might be understood as resolving ethical issues.

Whitbeck (1996) has addressed these issues in the context of engineering design. She argues that in the philosophical field of ethics, ethical problems are often misrepresented to stress the judgement aspect of the problem - whether a particular approach to resolving a problem is right or wrong - rather than the response aspect - the actions taken to address the ethical problem. The design process, Whitbeck suggests, provides an excellent analogy for thinking about how to resolve complex ethical problems.

By drawing an analogy, Whitbeck is implying that the two areas of problem resolution - the one in the ethical sphere, the other in the engineering design sphere - though similar, hence the analogy, are different in important respects. That is to say that, although engineering design problems might involve ethical issues, they are not themselves intrinsically ethical problems.

A view that brings the relationship between design and ethics much closer is that of Collier (2006) who describes a number of different ways in which architectural design can be construed as a moral activity. While Collier describes architectural design as a field that enables human flourishing - in effect an ethical aim - it is in her framing of 'practice' as realising 'goods' of various kinds where the locus of design and ethics is closest. She writes:

“Good practice engenders not only excellence of achievement but also virtuous relationships within the practice community” (p.310).

Leach (2009) echoes these comments in the field of software design showing that “the moral discourse is wrapped up in an aesthetics of code” (p.58). By closely observing the actual practice of Open Source software design Leach writes that:

“producing good code ... enhances the possibilities of human advancement. ‘Good Things’, things that work without redundancy, are both aesthetically pleasing, and morally positive in what they enable others to do.” (p.63)

It is the *practice* of ‘activities’ (assuming that ethics is a practice distinct from other types of practices) that involves the imagination in thinking about future states of affairs. Drawing on the pragmatist philosophy of John Dewey, Collier writes that imagination: “frames situations so as to grasp possibilities for constructive outcomes” (p.315). Johnson (1993) describes this process similarly as, “envisioning new possibilities”. Imagination—specifically moral imagination—Johnson argues, is a component of ethical thinking that should be carefully nurtured:

“We must cultivate moral imagination by sharpening our powers of discrimination, exercising our capacity for envisioning new possibilities, and imaginatively tracing out the implications of our metaphors, prototypes, and narratives.” (p.198)

‘Envisioning new possibilities’ is also a skill that is explicitly developed in design education, through formal and informal application of design theory, and especially by looking at implications through the use of prototypes. For designers, however, the types of ‘new possibilities’ envisioned are not obviously ethically motivated. Simon (1996), for example, emphasises the pleasurable aspects to the designer in exercising the imagination:

“the act of envisioning possibilities and elaborating them is itself a pleasurable and valuable experience ... designing is a kind of mental window shopping. Purchases do not have to be made to get pleasure from it.” (p.164)

Prima facie it seems quite a stretch to extend an act considered pleasurable in itself to one that would form the basis for good ethical behaviour, but this would seem to be quite a rarefied kind of pleasure - a pleasure obtained from intellectual work, rather than a pleasure derived from sensation. Described like this one could easily think of, say, a physician puzzling out the various ethical scenarios of purchasing a new and expensive drug as deriving a pleasure from the activity, if not the outcome. The *experience* of imagining, as the quote above suggests, is both pleasurable *and* valuable.

If a designer can, in Johnson’s words, ‘imaginatively [trace] out the implications of ... metaphors, prototypes, and narratives’ then an analysis of the role of imagination in the design process might provide an insight into a kind of ethical thinking. Particularly so, given the close aims of the design and ethics subject areas mentioned above. We might hypothesise that designers, explicitly taught to develop and make use of their imagination, could essentially solve ethical problems without explicitly addressing the problem’s ethical nature.

In the rest of the paper this hypothesis is rehearsed against a case study of urban planning by exploring a number of discourses involving ethics and imagination during the process of design. In building on previous studies (Lloyd and Busby, 2003; Lloyd, 2009), and considering the evidence of an urban design process, we conclude that designers, through exercising their imagination in designing, are able to resolve ethical problems without relying on the ethical discourses prevalent in both philosophy on the one hand, and the media on the other, which tend to rely on individual accounts of imagination

and explicit ethical awareness. The discourse of the design process suggests a more social idea of imagination (past and present) and design judgment that, although having a strong aesthetic component to it, is able to address ethical issues.

A CASE STUDY OF ROAD DESIGN

In September 1996 the 5.2 mile Bedford southern bypass, first conceived in a government white paper in 1983, and 8 years in planning, design, and construction, was nearing completion. The total cost for the project, which featured nine bridges as well as flood relief culverts, was £39 million. The Highways Agency were upbeat about the project. In a leaflet it was stated that the bypass was “designed to relieve congestion, improve road safety, and make journey times more reliable”. The bypass would “reduce personal injuries on Bedford’s roads by 166 and the number of fatalities by 6”. It would also be one of the first “environmentally sensitive” road schemes in the country “to blend the road into the landscape”. Several artist’s illustrations, produced in the pastoral style of John Constable, underlined the point rhetorically; in figure 1 the bypass is barely visible at all in the landscape. Just before opening 56,000 trees and shrubs had been planted with another 54,000 to follow. Overall the bypass would provide “tremendous benefits for people living and working in Bedford”.

Figure 1. An artist’s illustration of how the bypass would appear in the environment: ‘view from country way’.

Shortly before the official opening, however, a report appeared in *Bedfordshire on Sunday*, the local Sunday newspaper, which voiced concerns about the level of lighting on some sections of the bypass. Lighting was only in place at junctions. Wouldn’t this compromise road safety? the article asked. A local councillor was quoted as saying:

“considering the total cost of the bypass it is a pity lights could not be part of the package,

they often make all the difference and do so much to prevent accidents and save lives”

In the article the Highways Agency explained why certain sections of the bypass would be unlit. The volume of traffic, expected to be around 23,000 vehicles a day, was considered to be low. An expected accident rate had been arrived at, including an estimation of the likely number of accidents that would occur during the night. The overall conclusion were the figures quoted above: the bypass was likely to produce a reduction in injuries and fatalities. The overall accident rate of the bypass itself was considered to be low. The cost of the lighting (including the ‘cost’ of light pollution created and the increased energy use) outweighed the likely cost of the accidents.

Described like this the bypass would appear a morally good thing in a number of ways. Saving life, making existing lives more efficient, and helping the environment. It was opened on Wednesday 25th September by the government’s transport minister together with the local Member of Parliament and, naturally, help from local schoolchildren.

Two days after opening, at 10.30 on the evening of Saturday 28th September, during a “torrential downpour”, 5 young men travelling in a Mini Metro crashed on an unlit section of the bypass. One man died at the scene, two were taken in a critical condition to the emergency department at Addenbrookes hospital in Cambridge, one of whom died two days later. The other two men escaped with minor injuries.

Reporting on the deaths the local papers returned to the question of lighting on the bypass, questioning the decision to leave certain sections unlit.

After the first death the Highways Agency issued an official statement about safety checks that had been carried out prior to opening:

“Two safety audits were carried out by the Police and the County Council, one in the day and one in the night [with the implication being that lighting was looked at] ... both were passed satisfactorily, the road meets all safety specifications”

Letters to the local newspapers were at first critical of the lack of lighting. One remarked that “opening the new bypass without lights was almost like putting a ship to sea without a sail”. The prescient quote from the councillor was rehearsed, implying a lack of

common sense. Other letters remarked on the absence of crash barriers on elevated sections, one of which had formed the scene of the crash.

THE DESIGN PROCESS OF THE BEDFORD SOUTHERN BYPASS

The tenor of the criticism following the deaths on the bypass is that the designer (or designers) of the bypass should have made saving lives a priority above all other things. Indeed, this is how the problem might be put in an ethical case study; as a cost-benefit decision about where to channel resources so as to minimise harm. The implication is that the decision as to whether or not to light a section of the bypass is straightforwardly ethical. The criticism seems to suggest a failure of imagination on the part of the designers.

Is that a true reflection of how the design process was conducted? The public library in Bedford contains an archive of material relating to the design of the bypass and looking through the original documentation one begins to piece together a more complex picture of how the design process of the bypass was conducted. The archive contains seven boxes of material and the excerpts that follow relate to both the lighting design aspects of the bypass as well as other aspects that could broadly be construed as relating to some kind of value (for example, economic, aesthetic, environmental, etc.).

In the initial stages of the project the benefits that they bypass would bring are clearly evidenced and enumerated. Taking data from 1985-1989 It is noted that two existing trunk roads have particularly high accident records demonstrating that:

“heavily trafficked trunk roads have a substantial number of accidents ... modern high standard roads are much safer than old multi-purpose roads, so that transfer of traffic on the Bypass can be expected to bring about a worthwhile reduction in accidents”
(Statement on Traffic Effects and Economic Analysis).

Furthermore:

“vehicle users will collectively receive considerable economic benefits from the use of the Bypass from time savings and savings in vehicle operating costs ... the present value of these benefits (PVB) over 30 years is shown to

be £84.1m (low growth) to £136.2m (high growth) including accident savings.”

The overriding sense from the documentation is of an intensely participative process, a general adherence to standard road design principles, but a sensitivity to the particular context. Early in the design process two alternatives for the routing of the bypass are produced. A 1989 press notice from Bedfordshire County Council reads: “it is essential to have the public’s views on the proposed routes in order to help select one of the alternatives as a preferred option”. Thus, at an early stage, the ‘public’ are being involved in a key design decision.

Many documents in the archive relate to compulsory purchase orders, where people have been compensated after having to sell their land to the government to make way for the bypass. There are, however, surprises, as work on the bypass starts. A settlement from the late iron age / Roman period is unearthed and a report for English Heritage conducted which concludes:

“We do not consider that the Roman settlement remains meet the national criteria as worthy of preservation. We are prepared for these to be destroyed subsequent to archaeological recording.”

The heritage value of preserving the remains is not high enough when compared to the utility value bypass.

As the design progresses more general information about road design comes into play. In the following quote the predicted ‘flow’ of traffic merges seamlessly into a design decision:

“there is relatively little variation in traffic flow on the various sections of the bypass. The current predicted traffic flow for the design year (normally 15 years after opening) are well within the range where dual carriageways must be provided at both low and high growth scenarios. For the published scheme the predicted traffic flows warrant design Category 3 from Table 2 of Departmental Standard TD20/85 throughout this length.”

The impression given is one of a road being slowly designed from a list of pre-existing elements:

“a design speed of 120 kph *has been selected* for the Bypass; all design aspects such as stopping sight distance, horizontal and vertical

curvature and super-elevation have been correlated for this design speed.” (italics mine, statement by the Department of Transport’s representative).

A proposal for the width of the bypass is made by the Department of Transport with reference to a number of ‘carriageway standards’. The bypass is to be “an all-purpose dual 2-lane carriageway” with:

“the Department mindful of advice set down in the Departmental standards:

- (a) TD9/81 ‘Road Layout and Geometry - Highway Link Design’
 - (b) TD20/85 ‘Traffic Flows and Carriageway Width Assessment’
 - (c) TD11/82 ‘Use of Certain Departmental Standards in the Design and Assessment of Trunk Road Schemes’
- (2) The Departmental Advice Note TA30/82 ‘Choice between Options for Trunk Road Schemes’ ”

Functional and aesthetic considerations also contribute to the emerging form of the bypass. An early environmental statement discusses the subject of ‘grade separation’:

“with the continued growth in traffic, grade separated interchanges (i.e. two level) will be able to cater better for the predicted flows and are now more cost effective.”

There are other positive consequences to grade separation:

“The western part of the route has been designed with the main line in a cutting. This will reduce the visual intrusion to views from the South of Bedford.”

And grade separation leads to a further design decision:

“It is not proposed to light the main carriageways throughout, but lighting would be provided at the terminal roundabouts and the roundabout elements of the grade-separated interchanges.”

Late on in the project environmental factors are considered:

“[to] minimise the impact of the new bypass. Extensive planting will be undertaken at interchanges and on batter slopes, together

with tree planting in selected areas outside the lighting boundary. In certain locations, earthwork’s slopes will not be topsoiled but sown with wildflower seeds. In residential areas bunding and acoustic fencing will be provided to mitigate visual and noise effects.” (Highways Agency leaflet, 1994)

In considering the lighting for the bypass detailed economic appraisals of individual sections are produced where a number of factors are precisely quantified. For section Me 5400 - 7700 of the bypass, a 2.3km stretch, the accident rate is quoted at “0.17 Mvkm [Million vehicles per kilometer]”. Night accidents as a proportion of all accidents are given as “0.32”. The accident reduction proportion due to lighting is “0.3”, and the average cost of night accidents that would be saved by lighting is quoted as £69,504 for a high growth scenario, and £61513 for a low growth scenario.

Factored into the appraisal are the costs and effects of different types of lighting. There are twin arm and single arm designs, with varying column lengths, wattage, and lantern types. Capital cost for a single light varies from £850 to £1600, with operating costs varying similarly. Each portion of the road is considered in terms of the “Present Value of Benefits” and the “Present Value of Costs”. Under present value of benefits is an equation that allows “night time accidents saved” to be calculated. For section Me 5400 - 7700 it is formulated as:

$$\text{“Opening Year Traffic} \times 360 \times \text{Link Length} \times 0.17 \times 10.6 \times 0.32 \times 0.3\text{”}$$

(Economic Appraisal of Lighting Calculation Sheet No 8 of 16)

The figure for night time accidents saved comes out at 0.278228093 leading to a present value benefit of £129,900 which, when set against the present value of cost (£95,973) gives a “Net Present Value” of £33,927.

Explicit aesthetic factors to do with lighting are mentioned in a 1994 report on the placement of columns:

“Aesthetic considerations in relation to the Goldington Meadows viaduct require that column spacing and height must be sympathetic to the structural form of the viaduct.”

Lighting is looked at from a visual perspective as well. Drawings are produced that simulate how

Figure 2. Computer Aided Design simulation of lighting and layout for a small section of the Bedford Southern Bypass. Note the two different column types for the lighting, an important factor in determining cost and safety. This is a scan of an original document in the Bedford town library archive, UK.

various options might look, and the effects that they might have. Figures 2 and 3 show two different types of drawing. Figure 2 shows a perspective of a section of road and how lighting columns might be distributed along its length. Figure 3 shows the possible “visual intrusion” that lighting will cause to residential properties. It is interesting to compare these detailed visualisations of the bypass with the artist’s impression shown in figure 1, prior to construction work. Figure 1 can be read as being rhetorical, even misleading, while figures 2 and 3 are more focused on the practicalities of problem envisioning.

As the foregoing has illustrated Department of Transport standards play a huge part in the development of a road scheme, providing a body of information and guidance about all aspects of road design. There are factors, however, relating to the particular context of the Bedford Southern Bypass which need a non-standard approach. These are described as ‘relaxations and departures from standard’:

“In order to produce an economical design, while complying with the design speed and physical constraints, it has been necessary to incorporate a number of relaxations and departures from standard.”

A document called ‘the schedule of relaxations and departures’ itemises each deviation from standard practice. For example, one such item concerns: “stopping sight distance and horizontal radius” on a section of road. The relaxation is required because, for a 130 meter stretch, visibility is less than 120m, 40m less than the minimum design standard. The problem is described as:

“reduction of visibility in front of safety fence and bridge parapet combined with horizontal curvature 2 steps below Design Minimum.”
(Schedule of Relaxations and Departures)

Consideration of the ‘alignment geometry’ of the road leads to a solution: “widen verge by 3.3m increase horizontal Radius to 360m”. The cost associated with the solution is £99,000.

Figure 3. Ordnance Survey map overlaid with hand drawing to illustrate the visual impact of lighting for the Bedford Southern Bypass. The area in yellow indicates 'proposed high pressure sodium lighting', while the hatched areas in blue and red indicate the extent of visual intrusion to residential properties as a result of the scheme. This is a scan of an original document in the Bedford town library archive, UK.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The preceding narrative has been constructed by closely following documents produced during the process of design. These documents contain a level of detail and jargon that makes many words and sentences difficult to understand and follow for anyone unfamiliar with road design. The mathematical precision of the figures lends a mechanical, algorithmic view of the design process, an implied objectivity. One also gets the sense that this precise language, implicitly understood by the designers, is forming the design propositionally.

The narrative is necessarily selective in the way it presents documentary evidence but the differences in discourse between the design process and way the bypass is talked about following the deaths on the road is marked. The discourse of the process, while shot through with actual and implied references to value and benefit is not ethically charged. Instead there is an implied causality in the decisions being taken. X means Y, and Y means Z. There are no moral premises to the reasoning, just statements of

fact. This contrasts with the discourse following the deaths on the bypass which, as was mentioned previously, is explicitly ethical: more road lighting would save lives. While the reasoning following the deaths is very specifically aimed at saving lives, there is a kind of moral reasoning prior to the deaths - prior even to the design process - which is much more general and removed, but equally concerned with reducing deaths and injuries. Both can be considered as discourses of repair, making good something that has gone wrong. Following the deaths this discourse is targeted at repairing one particular thing: the lighting. Prior to the design process the discourse is centred around alleviating a clutch of problems relating to traffic build up. Design has only been used to address the second problem, not the first.

The narrative description reveals the strongly interconnected nature of the design process where a huge range of factors need to be not only weighed, but brought into balance. So the aesthetic value of placing street lighting in sympathy with the rhythm

of existing built form needs to be offset against problems of visibility for drivers, visual intrusion to residents, and environmental considerations. The documentation shows how these factors are visualised and quantified and also how design decisions are reached through a process of integration; good design decisions having positive consequences for other aspects of the scheme. The decision for grade separation, for example, which results in a portion of the main carriageway being placed in a cutting, has the positive consequence that the visual intrusion of lighting is minimised. The planting of trees outside of the lighting boundary not only meets environmental criteria, but again helps to mitigate visual and acoustic intrusion.

The process is played out in a balancing act of parts and wholes, and it is this relationship that is most difficult to understand for the non-designer. Individual parts can sometimes be very precisely quantified (a figure of night time accidents saved to nine decimal places, for example), but they need to be integrated into the whole that is the bypass. Scruton (1979) writes insightfully about the reason for this:

“In every serious task there are factors which, while of the greatest importance, cannot be assigned a relative value - not because their value is absolute, but because a man may not be able to judge in advance just when he is prepared to tolerate their remaining unsatisfied.” (p.29)

The envisioning of the bypass, then, is a slow working out of possibilities in many visual and textual representations, and given certain sets of existing and contingent information. The finished bypass itself is a kind of experiment looking at the subtle interplay of form and behaviour. A best guess that the benefits enumerated at the beginning of the project will be realised. Following Holt (1997), what that experiment contributes is further information that informs the standards that then play a role in shaping future road design.

The use of standards was a striking feature of the Bedford Southern Bypass and suggests that the concept of imagination in design is not a straightforwardly individual cognitive one. Many decisions were made with reference to a particular standard, and deviations from standards were carefully justified. The impression is of an imaginary ‘ideal’ bypass specified by Department of Transport

standards, and an actual bypass, fitted to a certain context. The actual working out of the design, then, was conceived in aggregated human behaviour (in traffic ‘flow’ for example) rather than the possibilities of what individuals, qua individuals, might do. This offers another distinction in the discourse pre and post the bypass deaths. The press and councillors formulate a discourse in the terms of individual action (which includes the designers’ omission to add enough street lighting), while the designers formulate the discourse in terms of aggregations and norms.

The physical form of the particular bypass also has a weight of inevitability about it; its very existence precluding other types of future that were thought out in alternative scenarios. Imagined deaths resulting from not having the bypass, i.e. bypasses that have remained in imagination, seem very abstract when set against actual deaths that have occurred from the particular bypass that has been built. Arguably the largest imaginative step in the process, and certainly an ethical one, was the initial idea that a bypass would, in many different ways, make life better.

Imagination, and the responsibility that comes with a putative failure of imagination would, then, be more usefully conceived collectively than individually. The exercise of imagination is clearly a necessary part of an individual creative process, however, as Collier (2006) proposes, it is the actual practice of design that is easiest to conceive ethically and in that practice the resolution of different imaginations is key.

The overarching design of the bypass can thus be framed ethically and clearly has had ethical effects. The individual parts to the design, however, appear as ethically neutral. The integrated nature of design decisions means that these parts are resolved seemingly without explicit ethical consideration - although conceivably conversations in the design office might have touched on ethical issues. This seems to suggest that aesthetic judgement, a feeling for balance between parts and wholes, can address ethical issues.

A professional discourse constructed through the particular case and the general standard has elements of what Kant (2005), in his *Critique of Judgment*, identifies as judgements of beauty. These judgements are not simply a matter of taste, but neither are they universal laws. There is room

for discussion in coming to such a judgement, and correspondingly room for dissent. Kant refers to these judgements as 'subjective universals', statements that appear objective and that people ought to agree with, but that to some degree are, nevertheless, questionable. The design process appears, on the evidence presented in this paper, to contain much that can be understood as this type of judgement. The fact that judgements of beauty, for Kant, lie somewhere between judgements of the good, on the one hand, and judgements of taste, on the other, implies that ethical things can be addressed indirectly through aesthetics. This is the main conclusion of the paper. That the design process is a way of resolving ethical problems without reference to 'the good'. The nature of design, that requires the imagination and discussion of alternatives at every stage, forces judgements of beauty to be made, but significantly not judgements of ethics.

In conclusion, this paper has tried to show the full scope of a design process, together with its consequences, in revealing several different discourses. The paper has done this by using documentation arising during, and following, the process as evidence to support interpretations made about these discourses. There is a strong empirical basis to the paper and this basis has been used to theorise the nature of the design process, particularly as it applies to ethical values. The early part of the paper discussed the close theoretical and practical relationships between design and ethics,

while the latter part of the paper discussed how the particular case of the bypass design can be understood ethically, particularly with respect to how decisions are made. The main contribution of the paper is to demonstrate how design can resolve ethical problems without using the ethical discourse common in either the philosophical literature, or the media. What the paper shows is that a more productive, perhaps more intuitive, way of addressing ethics is possible, and arguably desirable, through design.

REFERENCES

- Collier, J. (2006) The Art of Moral Imagination: Ethics in the Practice of Architecture, *Journal of Business Ethics*, 66, pp 307-317.
- Holt, J. (1997) The Designer's Judgment, *Design Studies*, 18, pp 113-123.
- Johnson, M. (1993) *Moral Imagination: Implications of the Cognitive Sciences for Ethics*, University of Chicago Press.
- Kant, I. (2005) *Critique of Judgment*, Dover Publications.
- Leach, J. (2009) Freedom Imagined: Morality and Aesthetics in Open Source Software Design, *Ethnos*, 74, pp 51-71.
- Lloyd, P.A., Busby, J.S. (2003) 'Things That Went Well - No Serious Accidents or Deaths' : Ethical Reasoning in a Normal Engineering Design Process, *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 9, pp 503-516.
- Lloyd, P.A. (2009) Ethical Imagination and Design, *Design Studies*, 30, pp 154-168.
- Scruton, R. (1979) *The Aesthetics of Architecture*, Methuen.
- Simon, H. (1996) *The Sciences of the Artificial (3rd Edition)*, MIT press.
- Whitbeck, C. (1996) Ethics as Design: Doing Justice to Moral Problems, *The Hastings Center Report*, May-June, 26, pp 9-16.